

White Light Reflectance Spectroscopy as a novel and noninvasive method for in situ wetting monitoring in membrane distillation

Dimosthenis Ioannou^{a,b}, Andreas Sapalidis^a, [Evangelos Gogolides^a](mailto:e.gogolides@inn.demokritos.gr)

^aInstitute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology, NCSR “Demokritos”, Aghia Paraskevi, 15341, Attica, Greece

^bSchool of Mechanical Engineering, National Technical University of Athens, Zografou, 15780, Attica, Greece

*e-mail: e.gogolides@inn.demokritos.gr

Keywords: membrane distillation, membrane wetting, membrane monitoring, detection, in-situ monitoring

ABSTRACT

Wetting, in membrane distillation (MD), is a major drawback appearing as a dynamic mechanism consisting of multiple stages. Normally, the liquid-air interface is placed on top of the membrane surface and its pores are only occupied with vapor. If liquid starts to penetrate the pores, surface wetting is followed by partial wetting that gradually develops until the fully wetted state occurs, compromising the operation. Usually, only the fully wetted state is assumed, and in fact indirectly, as liquid from the feedwater stream, containing soluble salts, passes through the pores and contaminates the permeate, thus increasing its conductivity. In this work, we present White Light Reflectance Spectroscopy (WLRS) as a novel and universal method for in-situ wetting monitoring in MD. By using WLRS it is possible to observe even slight movements of the liquid-air interface in real time, via changes in the reflectance spectrum, without compromising

the structural integrity of the membrane nor the module. Notably, the proposed method is applicable to any MD mode, unaffected by operating limitations and restrictions. With this noninvasive technique we can predict and observe all wetting stages, not only in the presence of surfactants in the feed stream, but also due to hydraulic pressure increase.

1. Introduction

Membrane distillation (MD), first introduced as a concept in the USA back in 1963,[1] is a thermally driven liquid separation and water treatment process. Currently, it receives a lot of attention for several industrial applications due to its ability to valorize low energy heat, modularity and the capacity to treat high salinity, challenging feedwaters [2] complementing in that way established processes such as reverse osmosis. In the simplest MD configuration, a hydrophobic, macroporous membrane with pore size typically ranging from 0.1 - 1.5 μm , separates two streams, a hot feedwater from a cold liquid, allowing just water vapor to pass through the pores from the hot stream and condense on the opposite side.[3–6] This method is employed not only for the treatment of high salinity solutions, but also in industrial wastes usually deriving from the metal, dying, tannery and food industries as well as municipal wastewaters where organic, inorganic and even toxic foulants might be present.[7,8] It is, therefore, essential for the membrane to resist wetting and provide a stable and long-lasting performance with high salt rejection (SR) efficiency in order to produce high purity water.

Since osmotic phenomena practically have no effect in MD, wetting, along with scaling and fouling, is considered one of the major drawbacks.[9,10] Membrane wetting is a dynamic mechanism consisting of multiple stages and states. First, the liquid-air interface is placed on top of the membrane surface, i.e. non-wetted state, where the pores are only occupied with vapor.[11,12] As liquid starts to move in the vicinity of the pore mouths, the second phase,

known as the surface-wetted state, begins. When the liquid air interface penetrates deeper into pores, partial wetting state is initiated. At this stage the permeate side is not yet contaminated, however as wetting develops, the distillate quality can be slightly compromised until the fully wetted state occurs, usually followed by permeate flux increase and a dramatic SR decrease. Therefore, it is obvious that when the membrane's anti-wetting properties fade, not only vapor but also liquid from the feedwater stream passes through the pores and contaminates the permeate side, thus compromising the operation.

To address the wetting issue, a great amount of effort is dedicated in the fabrication of various membrane types with the superhydrophobic ones proven capable to resist wetting, even in the presence of low surface tension substances such as surfactants.[13–24] Other studies report the processing of commercial membranes and their transformation to superhydrophobic using various methods like low-surface energy coatings, nanofiber formation and plasma processing.[25–29] Indeed, these efforts have, to some degree, succeeded in preventing or delaying wetting against some challenging feedwaters, however when eventually wetting occurs it is usually observed too late, and contamination of the product water is inevitable.

Various methods have been proposed, with some commonly employed, for the membrane wetting properties assessment and evaluation such as the contact angle (CA) and liquid entry pressure (LEP), while wetting can also be observed after-the-fact using scanning electron microscopy (SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) on the wetted membrane samples.[30,31] Notably, Jacob et al.[32] have developed a detection method of intruded dissolved tracer by which they were able to observe all wetting states by SEM-EDX. The disadvantage of all these methods is that they are not in-situ

and some are even destructive. Up to now, membrane wetting is indirectly assumed and associated with the increase in the conductivity of the permeate.

Research of recent literature suggests that numerous in-situ membrane monitoring methods have been proposed which can provide insight into wetting during MD. Jacob et al.[31] used a light transmission method that enabled them to notice wetting in real-time by observing changes in the light intensity. However, the presence of scaling or fouling may affect the signal and steady state water properties were required. Again, utilizing light intensity changes, Zhang et al.[33] were able to study wetting cartography and wetting dynamics by implementing a specific optical membrane cell, only applicable to vacuum membrane distillation (VMD). A noninvasive technique by means of real-time impedance spectroscopy was developed by Wong et al.[34] Even though electrodes on each side of the membrane were required, this method enabled the observation of various wetting states through impedance variations, with the drawback of introducing an added mass transfer resistance and system complexity. Impedance spectroscopy was also employed by Xiao et al.[35] for the spontaneous wetting process monitoring, however no application in MD was reported in the study. Another published work for probing pore wetting in real-time, involved cross-membrane impedance, but the method was limited only in direct contact setup (DCMD).[36] Ahmed et al.[37] fabricated an electrically conductive membrane to act as an electrode when ions of Na^+ and Cl^- were present on the permeate side, indicating wetting. The disadvantage of the method is that not only a specific membrane was required, but also the membrane itself increased the mass transfer resistance. It is evident that all the above-mentioned approaches suffer from severe limitations and disadvantages.

Fig. 1. WLRs for in situ wetting monitoring during MD setup schematic (a). Reflectance spectra for the different wetting states in MD including the non-wetted, the partially wetted and the fully wetted states (b).

In this work, we present White Light Reflectance Spectroscopy (WLRs) as a novel and universal method for in-situ wetting monitoring in MD. Using this method, which has been previously reported for monitoring underwater superhydrophobicity of flat surfaces and membranes,[38,39] we can observe even slight changes or movements of the liquid-air interface in real time without compromising the structural integrity of the membrane nor the module. Notably, WLRs is applicable to any MD mode (Air Gap, Vacuum, Sweeping Gas, etc.), without suffering from operating limitations and restrictions. By implementing this noninvasive technique, we are able to predict and observe wetting, via changes in the reflectance spectrum (Fig. 1), not only in the presence of surfactants but also due to hydraulic pressure. Specifically, wetting is induced by the gradual addition of Sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) in the saline feed solution, thus lowering the surface tension, and subsequently forcing the liquid-air interface to penetrate deeper into the pores. This translates to instantaneous reflectance drop indicating the initiation of the wetting

phase, while on the other hand, permeate conductivity started to increase (i.e., SR decrease) when feedwater's surface tension dropped below 55 mN/m. The same observation is made when isopropanol is added to the saline feed stream drastically reducing the surface tension from 72 to 27 mN/m. Again, the extreme sensitivity of the proposed method is confirmed by the instantaneous reflectance drop. Going one step further, we induce wetting through hydraulic pressure increase and by using WLRS we are able to monitor in real time all wetting states, a test that, to our knowledge, is reported for the first time in literature. Our method was even able to respond to small increments in the operating pressure, while salt rejection started to drop, indicating total wetting, only when the liquid entry pressure (LEP) of the membrane was reached.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Membrane materials

Hydrophobic, Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), flat-sheet membranes were kindly supplied by Donaldson (USA). The pore size is 1.5 μm and their structure features a 30-40 μm thick PTFE top layer (that is in contact with the feed solution), consisting of spider web-like formations of thin fibers (30-40 nm thick), and it is supported by a 110-120 μm thick Polypropylene (PP) bottom layer, consisting of thicker fibers (each being 25-30 μm thick approximately). The water static contact angle (WSCA) of the membranes is $135^\circ \pm 5^\circ$ on the topside and the backside, the LEP is 0.7 ± 0.05 bar and porosity value is $65 \pm 3\%$.

2.2. Membrane Distillation featuring WLRS setup

For the purposes of this study a Direct Contact Membrane Distillation (DCMD) setup is used, but our method does not have specific limitations and can be also applied to other MD setups

like the Air Gap (AGMD) and Vacuum MD (VMD). In DCMD, both sides of the membrane are in contact with liquids. The top side keeps contact with the saline feed solution containing 40 g/L NaCl and the backside is in contact with deionized water. Both the feed and the permeate water are stored in two 25 L polypropylene tanks and are circulated. The two streams maintain constant flowrates of 100 ml/min using two pumps (TCS micropump MGD1000P with integrated digital control) that are measured using electronic mass flow meters (Bronkhorst mini CORI-FLOW™ M14 and CORI-FLOW™ M54). The DCMD setup also features a control valve to adjust pressure on the feed side and a conductivity meter (HANNA HI700 with a HI7638 conductivity probe) to monitor the purity of the permeate (Fig. 2).[30] The membrane module is made of Acetal™, features an effective area of 27.5 cm² (5.25 cm x 5.25 cm) and is modified to hold a fiber optic reflection probe (6 + 1 fibers) from Ocean Optics (Fig. 1 a). The probe targets the center of the membrane's top surface from a 3 mm distance and is connected to a PC-driven spectrometer (Ocean Optics QE65000-ABS) (Fig. 2). The light source of the spectrometer is a broad-band deuterium/tungsten UV-VIS-NIR source operating in the range of 200 to 950 nm. In this work we monitor the wavelength range of 300-900 nm since in this area all involved liquids have zero absorbance and consequently any change in the reflectance spectra can be safely attributed only to wetting. Thus, when a membrane's surface is non-wetted the reflected ray, originating from the liquid-air interface at the top of the membrane's surface, is collected, and reflectance is measured. For as long as the surface remains in that state, the reflectance spectrum is stable. As soon as the liquid-air interface moves deeper into the pores, initiating the partially wetted state, the reflected ray weakens. This translates into a decrease in reflectance (Fig.1 b) that keeps on decreasing for as long as wetting develops, before reaching the lowest value which

is less than 2,5 % across all wavelengths. A detailed description of the WLRS method is also available in our previously published work.[38]

Fig. 2. Direct Contact Membrane Distillation (DCMD) combining White Light Reflectance Spectroscopy (WLRS) setup schematic.

2.3. Membrane Wetting Experiments

In this work we monitor membrane wetting induced by:

- i. surface tension decrease by the introduction of SDS,
- ii. surface tension decrease by the introduction of isopropanol,
- iii. operating pressure increase.

In the first test, 0.01 mM of SDS solution was gradually added to a standard saline feedwater (40 g/L NaCl, 72 mN/m), thus lowering the surface tension with every SDS addition, resulting, after 25 steps (duration of each step is 10 minutes to allow stable conditions) to a final SDS concentration of 0.2 mM corresponding to a surface tension of 37.9 ± 0.06 mN/m. The same

procedure is followed when isopropanol is used, to gradually decrease the surface tension down to 27.2 ± 0.06 mN/m, after a total of 11 steps (again, the duration of each step is 10 minutes), reaching a final isopropanol concentration of 4.85 M (29 % w/w).

For the third test, we induce wetting through pressure starting from 0.1 bar, and we proceed with 0.1 bar increments, each followed by an interval of 5 min. The increase of pressure continued even above the LEP of the membrane, that is 0.7 bar, and the test ended at a final pressure value of 1.1 bar due to permeate's conductivity value rising beyond the conductivity meter's range (> 200 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Surfactant-induced membrane wetting using SDS

The sensitivity of the proposed method for wetting monitoring, compared to traditional permeate conductivity measurement, is evaluated. Wetting is induced with the introduction of SDS, a common surfactant, in the saline feed solution. Using SDS the surface tension was gradually reduced from 72 mN/m to 37.9 mN/m, in the span of 25 consecutive steps. As shown in Fig. 3 a, the reflectance spectrum of the active membrane's surface started to decrease instantaneously with the surface tension reduction, even for decrements less than 5 mN/m. On the contrary, surface tension had to drop below 55 mN/m, until any changes in the conductivity of the permeate could be detected (Fig. 3 b). By further addition of SDS into the feed solution, SR decreased down to 99.94 % at the end of the experiment, while the normalized reflectance at 300 nm shows a total reduction of 15 %. Even though, at the end of the test, the quality of the permeate was not optimal, the anti-wetting properties of the membrane did not fade completely, denoting that only partial wetting occurred. However, the initial wetting stages were indicated,

even at the very first steps of the experiment, via reflectance drops, demonstrating the ability of the proposed method to real-time monitor the dynamic nature of wetting phenomena in MD.

Fig. 3. Reflectance spectra at different feed surface tension values. Feed water includes 40g/L NaCl and various SDS concentrations corresponding to the surface tension values shown in the legend (a). Normalized reflectance at 300 nm and salt rejection versus surface tension (b). Reflectance starts to drop instantly as surface tension lowers, indicating the wetting transition phase, while salt rejection starts to decrease when surface tension drops below 55 mN/m.

3.2. Low surface tension substance -induced membrane wetting using isopropanol

As an additional test, the surface tension of the feed solution, again starting from 72 mN/m, was reduced to 27.2 mN/m with the gradual addition of isopropanol, after a total of 11 steps. During this test, the fully wetted state was achieved, as proven by the dramatic SR decrease which reached the final value of 98.2 %, by the end of the experiment. First, a linear decrease in both reflectance and salt rejection was observed down to 45 mN/m. During these steps, the initial wetting stages occurred (surface and partial wetting). However, when surface tension dropped

below that critical value, reflectance exhibited a dramatic reduction of 50 % within a 5 mN/m decrement (Fig. 4). This significant change enabled a clear prediction of the impending wetting that would follow shortly thereafter. Indeed, a steep decline in SR was observed when surface tension dropped below 27 mN/m. In this case, the sensitivity of WLRS indicated the initiation of the fully wetted state, several steps before any crucial conductivity increase could be detected. This demonstrates the adequacy of the proposed method in real life applications, where operation failures could be efficiently predicted and avoided.

Fig. 4. Reflectance spectra at different feed surface tension values. Feed water includes 40g/L NaCl and various isopropanol concentrations corresponding to the surface tension values shown in the legend (a). Normalized reflectance at 300 nm and salt rejection versus surface tension (b).

3.3. Pressure-induced membrane wetting

Similar observations were made in the pressure-induced wetting test. The initial pressure value was 0.1 bar, which is the pressure required to achieve zero trans-membrane pressure in the experimental setup, and a final value of 1.1 bar was reached at the end of the experiment. Notably, a 25 % drop in reflectance was observed within the first 0.1 bar increment, followed by

an additional 15 % drop in the second increment (Fig. 5). This significant reflectance reduction is attributed to an increase in the distance of the membrane's surface from the monitoring probe (resulting in reduced signal), due to hydraulic pressure increase causing the membrane to curve. This observation suggests that, not only movements of the liquid-air interface, but even curvatures of the membrane's surface due to changes in the operating parameters can be detected using WLRS. Subsequently, a continuous and linear reflectance decrease was measured until the end of the experiment, while SR only started to drop when the LEP value of the membrane (that is 0.7 bar) was exceeded. To our knowledge, this is the first time an in-situ monitoring of pressure-induced wetting is reported in literature, further proving the capabilities of the proposed method in real-life applications and systems, where challenging conditions commonly occur.

Fig. 5. Reflectance spectra at different MD operating pressures (a). Normalized reflectance at 300 nm and salt rejection versus MD operating pressure (b).

4. Conclusions

Herein, the capability of WLRS for the in-situ wetting monitoring in MD is demonstrated. The sensitivity of the proposed method enables real time responses to even slight changes and

movements of the liquid-air interface corresponding to the different wetting stages. Specifically, successful wetting monitoring and prediction of the fully wetted state is achieved by the proposed method, not only to surfactant-induced, but also to pressure-induced wetting. Reflectance dropped instantaneously when SDS was introduced in the feed stream, indicating the initial wetting stages, while SR started to drop when surface tension reduced below 55 mN/m. Similarly, a steep decline in reflectance was observed when isopropanol was introduced in the feed stream to lower the surface tension, several steps before a conductivity increase could be detected. Going one step further, WLRS was able to respond to even small increments in hydraulic pressure of the feed stream, during pressure-induced wetting, a test that to our knowledge has not yet been reported in literature. Again, wetting was successfully indicated, via changes in reflectance, before the LEP value of the membrane was reached causing total wetting and SR reduction.

Acknowledgments

Financial support has also been provided by the Horizon 2022 EIC Transition Open project SuperClean.

The publication of the article in OA mode was financially supported by HEAL-Link.

References

- [1] B.R. Bodell, Distillation of Saline Water Using Silicone Rubber Membrane, United States

- Pat. (1968) 1–4.
- [2] D.M. Warsinger, J. Swaminathan, E. Guillen-Burrieza, H.A. Arafat, J.H. Lienhard V, Scaling and fouling in membrane distillation for desalination applications: A review, *Desalination*. 356 (2015) 294–313. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2014.06.031>.
- [3] A. Alkudhiri, N. Darwish, N. Hilal, Membrane distillation: A comprehensive review, *Desalination*. 287 (2012) 2–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2011.08.027>.
- [4] L.M. Camacho, L. Dumée, J. Zhang, J. Li, M. Duke, *Advances in Membrane Distillation for Water Desalination and Purification Applications*, (2013) 94–196. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w5010094>.
- [5] K.W. Lawson, D.R. Lloyd, Membrane distillation, *J. Membr. Sci.* 124 (1997) 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00216-011-4733-9>.
- [6] R.W. Schofield, A.G. Fane, C.J.D. Fell, Heat and mass transfer in membrane distillation, *J. Memb. Sci.* 33 (1987) 299–313. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-7388\(00\)80287-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-7388(00)80287-2).
- [7] A.R. Bielefeldt, *Water Treatment, Industrial, Encycl. Microbiol.* (2009) 569–586. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-012373944-5.00163-2>.
- [8] I. Tournis, D. Tsiourvas, A. Papavasiliou, N.K. Boukos, *Environmental Science Water Research & Technology* membrane distillation-based desalination, (2022) 2373–2380. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d2ew00407k>.
- [9] H. Chamani, J. Woloszyn, T. Matsuura, D. Rana, C.Q. Lan, Pore wetting in membrane distillation: A comprehensive review, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 122 (2021) 100843. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmatsci.2021.100843>.

- [10] T. Horseman, Y. Yin, K.S. Christie, Z. Wang, T. Tong, S. Lin, Wetting, Scaling, and Fouling in Membrane Distillation: State-of-the-Art Insights on Fundamental Mechanisms and Mitigation Strategies, *ACS ES&T Eng.* 1 (2021) 117–140. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsestengg.0c00025>.
- [11] M. Gryta, Long-term performance of membrane distillation process, *J. Memb. Sci.* 265 (2005) 153–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2005.04.049>.
- [12] K. Karakulski, M. Gryta, Water demineralisation by NF/MD integrated processes, *Desalination.* 177 (2005) 109–119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2004.11.018>.
- [13] L. Zheng, K. Wang, D. Hou, X. Jia, Z. Zhao, Hierarchically-structured superhydrophobic POSS/PVDF composite membrane for anti-fouling and anti-wetting membrane distillation, *Desalination.* 526 (2022) 115512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2021.115512>.
- [14] Q. Sun, Z. Yang, C. Hu, C. Li, G. Yan, Z. Wang, Facile preparation of superhydrophobic PVDF microporous membranes with excellent anti-fouling ability for vacuum membrane distillation, *J. Memb. Sci.* 605 (2020) 118106. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2020.118106>.
- [15] N.F. Himma, N. Prasetya, S. Anisah, I.G. Wenten, Superhydrophobic membrane: Progress in preparation and its separation properties, *Rev. Chem. Eng.* (2018) 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1515/revce-2017-0030>.
- [16] C. Su, T. Horseman, H. Cao, K.S.S. Christie, Y. Li, S. Lin, Robust Superhydrophobic Membrane for Membrane Distillation with Excellent Scaling Resistance, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b04362>.

- [17] Z. Xiao, R. Zheng, Y. Liu, H. He, X. Yuan, Y. Ji, D. Li, H. Yin, Y. Zhang, X.M. Li, T. He, Slippery for scaling resistance in membrane distillation: A novel porous micropillared superhydrophobic surface, *Water Res.* 155 (2019) 152–161.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2019.01.036>.
- [18] L. Deng, P. Li, K. Liu, X. Wang, B.S. Hsiao, Robust superhydrophobic dual layer nanofibrous composite membranes with a hierarchically structured amorphous polypropylene skin for membrane distillation, *J. Mater. Chem. A.* 7 (2019) 11282–11297.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/c9ta02662b>.
- [19] Z. Li, J. Marlina, D. Pranantyo, B.L. Nguyen, C.H. Yap, A porous superhydrophobic surface with active air plastron control for drag reduction and fluid impalement resistance †, (2019) 16387–16396. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9ta02745a>.
- [20] Z. Zhu, L. Zhong, T. Horseman, Z. Liu, G. Zeng, Z. Li, S. Lin, W. Wang, Superhydrophobic-omniphobic membrane with anti-deformable pores for membrane distillation with excellent wetting resistance, *J. Memb. Sci.* 620 (2021) 118768.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2020.118768>.
- [21] K.J. Lu, D. Zhao, Y. Chen, J. Chang, T.S. Chung, Rheologically controlled design of nature-inspired superhydrophobic and self-cleaning membranes for clean water production, *Npj Clean Water.* 3 (2020) 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41545-020-0078-2>.
- [22] Y. Chen, M. Tian, X. Li, Y. Wang, A.K. An, J. Fang, T. He, Anti-wetting behavior of negatively charged superhydrophobic PVDF membranes in direct contact membrane distillation of emulsified wastewaters, *J. Memb. Sci.* 535 (2017) 230–238.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2017.04.040>.

- [23] J.A. Kharraz, A.K. An, Patterned superhydrophobic polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) membranes for membrane distillation: Enhanced flux with improved fouling and wetting resistance, *J. Memb. Sci.* 595 (2020) 117596.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.117596>.
- [24] E. Gontarek-Castro, R. Castro-Muñoz, M. Lieder, New insights of nanomaterials usage toward superhydrophobic membranes for water desalination via membrane distillation: A review, *Crit. Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 0 (2021) 1–46.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10643389.2021.1877032>.
- [25] C. Yang, X.M. Li, J. Gilron, D. feng Kong, Y. Yin, Y. Oren, C. Linder, T. He, CF₄ plasma-modified superhydrophobic PVDF membranes for direct contact membrane distillation, *J. Memb. Sci.* 456 (2014) 155–161.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2014.01.013>.
- [26] L.N. Nthunya, L. Gutierrez, E.N. Nxumalo, A.R. Verliefe, S.D. Mhlanga, M.S. Onyango, F-MWCNTs/AgNPs-coated superhydrophobic PVDF nanofibre membrane for organic, colloidal, and biofouling mitigation in direct contact membrane distillation, *J. Environ. Chem. Eng.* 8 (2020) 103654. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2020.103654>.
- [27] M. Liu, Y. Luo, D. Jia, Polydimethylsiloxane-based superhydrophobic membranes: Fabrication, durability, repairability, and applications, *Polym. Chem.* 11 (2020) 2370–2380. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9py01861a>.
- [28] W. Jia, J.A. Kharraz, P.J. Choi, J. Guo, B.J. Deka, A.K. An, Superhydrophobic membrane by hierarchically structured PDMS-POSS electro spray coating with cauliflower-shaped beads for enhanced MD performance, *J. Memb. Sci.* 597 (2020) 117638.

- <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.117638>.
- [29] D. Ioannou, Y. Hou, P. Shah, K. Ellinas, M. Kappl, A. Sapalidis, V. Constantoudis, H.-J. Butt, E. Gogolides, Plasma-Induced Superhydrophobicity as a Green Technology for Enhanced Air-Gap Membrane Distillation, *SSRN Electron. J.* (2022).
<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4295130>.
- [30] E. Balis, A. Sapalidis, G. Pilatos, E. Kouvelos, C. Athanasekou, C. Veziri, P. Boutikos, K.G. Beltsios, G. Romanos, Enhancement of vapor flux and salt rejection efficiency induced by low cost-high purity MWCNTs in upscaled PVDF and PVDF-HFP hollow fiber modules for membrane distillation, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 224 (2019) 163–179.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2019.04.067>.
- [31] P. Jacob, B. Dejean, S. Laborie, C. Cabassud, An optical in-situ tool for visualizing and understanding wetting dynamics in membrane distillation, *J. Memb. Sci.* 595 (2020) 117587. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2019.117587>.
- [32] P. Jacob, S. Laborie, C. Cabassud, Visualizing and evaluating wetting in membrane distillation: New methodology and indicators based on Detection of Dissolved Tracer Intrusion (DDTI), *Desalination.* 443 (2018) 307–322.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2018.06.006>.
- [33] T. Zhang, S. Laborie, C. Cabassud, Optical method for in operando study of membrane distillation wetting: Development for desalination and potential for exploring wetting dynamics, *Desalination.* 539 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2022.115944>.
- [34] P.W. Wong, V.M.W. Yim, J. Guo, B.S. Chan, B.J. Deka, A.K. An, Noninvasive Real-

- Time Monitoring of Wetting Progression in Membrane Distillation Using Impedance Spectroscopy, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 56 (2022) 535–545.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c04433>.
- [35] J. Xiao, Q. Sun, L. Liu, Z. Ding, Monitoring the spontaneous wetting process of hydrophobic microporous membrane assisted by alternating current impedance spectroscopy, *Chinese J. Chem. Eng.* 39 (2021) 96–102.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjche.2020.08.055>.
- [36] Y. Chen, Z. Wang, G.K. Jennings, S. Lin, Probing Pore Wetting in Membrane Distillation Using Impedance: Early Detection and Mechanism of Surfactant-Induced Wetting, *Environ. Sci. Technol. Lett.* 4 (2017) 505–510.
<https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.estlett.7b00372>.
- [37] F.E. Ahmed, B.S. Lalia, R. Hashaikeh, Membrane-based detection of wetting phenomenon in direct contact membrane distillation, *J. Memb. Sci.* 535 (2017) 89–93.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2017.04.035>.
- [38] A. Smyrnakis, D. Ioannou, K. Ellinas, A. Tserepi, E. Gogolides, Real-Time Monitoring and Quantification of Underwater Superhydrophobicity, *Adv. Mater. Interfaces.* 9 (2022) 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.202101393>.
- [39] D. Ioannou, P. Shah, K. Ellinas, M. Kappl, A. Sapalidis, H.J. Butt, E. Gogolides, Anti-fouling plasma treated membranes with stable superhydrophobic properties for membrane distillation, submitted to *J. Memb. Sci.* on 31st of May, 2023.